

Mapping gully affected areas based on Sentinel 2 imagery and digital elevation model

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Abstract—Gully poses a great threat to agricultural production and ecological environment. Mapping accurate gully affected areas plays an important role in regional environmental monitoring and management. In this paper, an object-based image analysis method based on Google Earth Engine (OBIA-GEE) for mapping gully affected areas was proposed by using Sentinel 2 imagery and AW3D 30 DEM data. The method utilized the simple non-iterative clustering (SNIC) segmentation and the random forest (RF) algorithm to segment imagery and map gully affected areas. And terrain skeleton lines were further used to optimize the mapping results. The proposed method was applied to five study areas with different landform types on the Chinese Loess Plateau, and the results showed that the method achieved good performance with the overall accuracy of 86.44%, user's accuracy of 84.97%, and producer's accuracy of 83.90%. The OBIA-GEE method provides the possibility of large-scale gullies mapping, which is beneficial to monitor gullies and manage soil erosion.

I. INTRODUCTION

Gully erosion is a typical form of soil erosion that shapes surface morphology, resulting in development of gullies [1, 2]. Accurately mapping gully affected areas not only provides a basis for regional soil and water conservation but also provides important guidance for regional environmental management [3].

There are several gully affected areas mapping methods, including visual interpretation methods (VIM), pixel-based methods (PBM), object-based image analysis (OBIA) methods and deep learning (DL) methods, but the performance of these methods still need to be improved. The VIM method relies on manual visualization, which is labour intensive and time consuming [4]. The PBM based on remote sensing imagery and digital elevation model (DEM) are subject to the phenomena of

salt and pepper noise and the topographic features of different study areas [3, 5], while these can be avoided by the OBIA method. The OBIA method can improve the mapping's accuracy to some extent [6, 7], but the accuracy at a large scale still needs to be improved, mainly due to the limitations of image resolution [8]. Studies have used less costly high-resolution Google Earth images with DEM data to map gully affected areas [9], but Google Earth images do not provide a clear enough spectral signal to distinguish gullies with drastic changes in internal morphology [10, 11]. Besides, the DL methods are limited to a large amount of pixel-level or object-level sample data to perform well [12].

Considering gully affected areas have distinct geometric features, textural information, topographic features, and complex dynamic spectral characteristics [13], the OBIA method and spectral information as well as phenological indicators based on temporal patterns, such as normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI), should be used to map gully affected areas. The Google Earth Engine (GEE) platform has gradually become an important platform for large-scale geological analysis [14, 15, 16]. And Sentinel-2 images offer the possibility of mapping gully affected areas [17, 18]. Therefore, the objective of this paper was to propose an accurate object-based image analysis method based on Google Earth Engine (OBIA-GEE) for large-scale Loess Plateau gully affected areas mapping.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials

Gully erosion is very serious and the degree of development of loess gullies varied on the Loess Plateau [19, 20]. Hence, five

typical Loess Plateau erosion areas representing different landform types were selected as the study area herein (Fig. 1(a-e)). The specific definition of a gully affected area is that the upper boundary is along the gully shoulder line, and the lower boundary is the channel with a flow accumulation threshold area greater than 50 km² according to the boundary of erosion and hydrology [21].

All Sentinel 2 surface reflectance data (https://developers.google.com/earth-engine/datasets/catalog/COPERNICUS_S2_SR) with less than 20% cloudiness in 2020 were selected and masked cloud on GEE. The median images of red, green, blue, NIR bands and NDVI index were obtained every three months as a unit, and a total of 20 images were produced to provide dynamic time series spectral information. In addition, AW3D30 DEM data derived from GEE (https://developers.google.com/earth-engine/datasets/catalog/JAXA_ALOS_AW3D30_V1_1) with 30-meter resolution were used to calculate topographic factors and terrain textural information. A total of 5,150 training samples in point format were generated randomly by the randomPoints function and manually labelled as gully or non-gully on GEE (Fig. 1(a-e)). The validation samples in object format were manually drawn based on high-resolution Google Earth images, having an 8 km² draw for each study area for a total of 40 km² (Fig. 1(V1-V10)).

Figure 1. Map of the study area and samples for training and validation. (a) Loess tablelands, SA1; (b) Loess long-ridge fragmented tablelands, SA2; (c) Loess ridge hills and gullies, SA3; (d) Loess hills and gullies, SA4; (e) Loess-aeolian and dune transition zones, SA5. The distribution of training samples (a-b) and validation samples (V1-V10) for each study area.

Methods

This paper proposed an object-based image analysis method based on Google Earth Engine (OBIA-GEE) for mapping large-scale loess gully affected areas. The main steps were (i) image segmentation, which used SNIC algorithm to create objects based on heterogeneity of each pixel value, (ii) feature selection and

random forest, which calculated four types of features selected herein as input data to the RF algorithm to map gully affected areas, and (iii) terrain skeleton utilization for optimization and accuracy assessment, which improved mapping results by removing river areas from gully affected areas and assessed mapping accuracy based on object samples. Fig. 2 shows the techniques flow chart.

A. Image Segmentation

Principal component analysis (PCA) was performed using spectral median images of Sentinel-2 with 10-meter resolution to extract the principal components herein. The top five PCA components were selected for image segmentation. The super-pixel image segmentation method, simple non-iterative clustering (SNIC) algorithm on GEE was used for segmentation due to its superior segmentation performance [22]. Considering the irregular characteristics of gully affected areas and comparing different segmentation results with different parameter sets, the main parameters of SNIC algorithm were set: size = 8, compactness = 0.1, connectivity = 8, and neighbourhood size = 256.

Figure 2. Techniques flow chart.

B. Feature Selection and Random Forest

Four types of features with a total of 50 were calculated for each object after image segmentation, including spectral, textural, geometric and topographic features. The spectral median images of red, green, blue, NIR and NDVI were acquired, for a total of 20 images. Topographic factors with slope, surface cut depth (SCD), and positive and negative terrain (PNT) indices were calculated herein to provide terrain information [23]. The terrain textural information was obtained by utilizing the gray level co-occurrence matrix (GLCM) with a 3×3 kernel size for the above three topographic factors, and a total of 24 images of textural information were produced [24]. The geometric features of each object with area, height and width were calculated herein.

Random forest (RF) algorithm is one of the most popular predictive classification algorithms due to its simplicity and ease of implementation and superior classification performance [25].

In this paper, the smileRandomForest classifier on GEE was applied to map gully affected areas, with 50 features and 5,150 training samples as input data, and the number of decision trees was set to 100 with other parameters (e.g., bagFraction set to 0.5, maxNodes set to no limit) set to default according to the RF training results.

C. Optimization and Accuracy Assessment

Terrain skeleton lines obtained by the hydrological analysis of AW3D30 DEM data with a flow accumulation threshold of 50 km² were used to optimize the OBIA-GEE mapping results according to the definition of gully affected area herein. Then the distance accumulation was applied to obtain the river area, and the extracted terrain skeleton lines with the slope of DEM data were used as the input data. Finally, river areas were intersected with the gully affected area mapping results to obtain the gully affected areas with the river removed.

To judge the accuracy of the mapping results, the confusion matrix approach was used to perform accuracy assessment herein [26]. The overall accuracy (OA), producer’s accuracy (PA) and user’s accuracy (UA) were calculated for mapping results after optimization.

III. RESULTS

Table I shows the accuracy assessment of the gully affected area results for each study area and all study areas. The OA of all study areas reached 86.44%, and the PA and UA were 83.90% and 84.97%, indicating that the proposed method was applicable to the various landform types of the Loess Plateau and had good performance. The OA of gully affected areas in each study area was higher than 81%. SA3 (87.15%), SA2 (84.37%), and SA4 (82.68%) had higher UA values, which means that commission error was smaller and the omission error was relatively larger in the area of intense surface erosion. Moreover, SA1 (91.16%) and SA5 (90.34%) had higher PA values, which means that the omission error was smaller and the commission error was relatively larger in the area of less erosion intensity.

TABLE I. THE CONFUSION MATRIX OF THE GULLY AFFECTED AREA RESULTS FOR EACH STUDY AREA AND ALL STUDY AREAS.

Study area	PA (%)	UA (%)	OA (%)
SA1	91.16	83.81	95.67
SA2	76.41	84.37	86.01
SA3	83.32	87.15	83.54
SA4	79.96	82.68	81.90
SA5	90.34	85.46	85.37
All study areas	83.90	84.97	86.44

Fig. 3 shows magnified views of mapping results for each study area with different landform types. The mapping results had reasonable structural characteristics, which reflected the spatial continuity of the gullies and the suitability of the method for different landforms. Magnified views of SA2, SA3 and SA4, where the development of gullies was higher and the area of inter-gully land was smaller, so some inter-gully areas were misclassified as gully affected areas. For the loess tablelands (SA1), the gully affected areas were generally mapped accurately. For the loess-aeolian and dune transition zones (SA5), the erosion degree was relatively small, and the mapping results of the gully affected areas were consistent with the actual distribution.

Figure 3. Gully affected area mapping results were overlaid on Sentinel images and DEM images. (a) and (b): SA1; (c) and (d): SA2; (e) and (f): SA3; (g) and (h): SA4; (i) and (j): SA5.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

An OBIA-GEE method was proposed for the rapid mapping of large-scale loess gullies in this paper. By using the SNIC segmentation and RF algorithm with multiple features, the loess gully affected areas with different landform types were mapped. And terrain skeleton lines were used to optimize the gully affected area mapping results. The results showed that the method achieved good performance, with the OA of 86.44% for all study areas, the UA of 84.97%, and the PA of 83.90%. For each landform type, the OA was higher than 81.5%. Moreover, the OBIA-GEE method is convenient due to the advantages of GEE platform. The proposed method will be beneficial for studies related to monitoring gullies and managing soil erosion. This work also provides a new perspective for large-scale landform mapping and the basic idea of this method can be extended to map multiple types of topographic objects.

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